

INVESTIGATION ON THE INTERFACE COATING WITHOUT STRENGTH DEGRADATION OF FIBER IN OXIDE FIBERS REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties, especially the tensile strength of ceramic matrix composites are primarily determined by the tensile strength of the continuous fibers in the woven fabrics. Therefore, high retention of fiber tensile strength after fiber pretreating/coating and forming processing is expected. In the present work, we developed an efficient lanthanum phosphate interface coating on woven oxide ceramic fabrics by vacuum infiltration plus online liquid precipitation. These interface coatings minimize the tensile strength degradation for woven oxide ceramic fabrics during fiber coating and matrix processing. The retention of tensile strength for both kinds of oxide ceramic woven is upper to 70% after coating processing. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of ceramic matrix composites at high temperature are also optimized. For instance, the tensile strength retention at 1200°C for alumina fiber reinforced composites is promoted ~70% compared with the situation without the interface coating, while tensile strength of quartz fiber reinforced oxide composites increased more than 50%. The investigation have potential application for preparing composites in long service life in oxidizing and high temperature environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the outstanding performance of continuous fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMCs), such as high weight, high strength, high temperature tolerance, and potential applications in aerospace and automotive field in aggressive operating environments at extremely high temperature, they attracted more and more considerations.^[1-3]

Oxide fiber reinforced oxide ceramic matrix composite is kind of CMCs (oxide/oxide CMCs). These kind of composites are much cheaper than non oxide CMCs, such as C/SiC and SiC/SiC CMCs, and have superior environmental stability as well. The most important is, because all constituents of these CMCs are the oxides, they have superior resistance to oxidation under typical turbine engine conditions, that means they can be used in oxidation, particularly in combustion environments.^[4-5] The mechanical properties, especially the tensile strength of ceramic matrix composites is primarily determined by the tensile strength of the continuous fibers in the woven fabrics. Moreover, the high temperature mechanical properties of the oxide/oxide CMCs is strongly related to the tailored interface between the matrix and reinforced fibers. Therefore, high retention of fiber tensile strength after fiber pretreating/coating and forming processing is expected. Carbon and boron nitride are the usual fiber coatings, but they have poor oxidation resistance. In this case, oxide or phosphate coating, especially LaPO₄^[6-8], have been demonstrated to be effective for maintaining there's high temperature stability and improving the matrix-dominated properties.

In the present work, we developed an efficient lanthanum phosphate interface coating on woven oxide ceramic fabrics by vacuum infiltration plus online liquid precipitation. These interface coatings minimize the tensile strength degradation for woven oxide ceramic fabrics during fiber coating and matrix processing. The retention of tensile strength for alumina fiber is ca. 90%, while quartz fiber is ca. 78% after coating processing. Furthermore, the

mechanical properties of ceramic matrix composites at high temperature are also optimized. For instance, the tensile strength retention at 1200°C for alumina fiber reinforced composites is promoted ~70% compared with the situation without the interface coating, while tensile strength of quartz fiber reinforced oxide composites increased more than 50%. The investigation have potential applicaion for preparing composites in long service life in oxidizing and high temperature environments.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials preparation

3D angle interlock woven fabrics of alumina fiber and quartz fiber (Tianjin Polytech University, China) are used for all experiments. The thickness of the woven fabrics preforms were 10-30 mm, length and width were 260mm. Both kinds of preforms were desized at 400-600 °C for 3 hours in air. Interface coating precursor solution prepared was similar with Hay R. S. recipe^[7], lanthanum nitrate (Strem Chemicals, Newburyport, MA, US) and citric acid (Alfa Aesar) which dissolved in deionized water, and then mixed with phosphoric acid (J&K Chem., China). The La:citrate:P ratio was 1:(2-3.5):1, which yield 50g/L LaPO₄ in mixed solution.

2.2 Processing of interface coating and composites preparation

Interface coatings for the woven fabrics preforms were created by vacuum infiltration plus in-situ liquid precipitation, in which case the precursor solution could penetrate into thick preforms completely. Silica sol precursor was used for infiltrating in woven performs. Cycled infiltration with vacuum or pressure and subsequent heat-treatments were performed to obtain the dense composites.

2.3 Characterization

Interface coating surface morphology and cross-section were both characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM, Appolo 300, CamScan). X-ray Diffractometer (XRD, D8 Advance, Bruker) is used for confirm the coating substance and crystal phase transformation of composites during high temperature experiences.

Tensile strengths of coated and uncoated alumina/quartz fibers were evaluated by universal tester (AGS-X 300, Shimudazu, Japan) using filament bundles which experienced desizing, interface coating or high temperature heat treatments. Tensile strengths of composites were performed by materials testing machine (Zwick Z100, Germany).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of LaPO₄ coating on alumina/quartz fabric preforms

Uniform coatings for 3D alumina/quartz fabric preforms are prepared by vacuum infiltration plus in-situ liquid precipitation, which means infiltrated the liquid precursor by vacuum condition first and subsequently allow the in-situ liquid precipitation of LaPO₄ on the preforms. The thickness of the monazite coating can be ranged from 200 nm~1.0 μm which controlled by concentration of the liquid precursor, PH value, precipitate temperature, precipitation time and anneal temperature. Figure 1 shows the LaPO₄ coating morphology during different precipitation times on the surface of alumina fibers under the optimized precipitate conditions. After five times precipitation, uniform and dense layers are formed.

Figure 1: LaPO₄ coating morphology on alumina fibers during different precipitation times

As observed in figure 2, around 200~300nm LaPO₄ nanorods formed at the initial precipitation, until spread over the whole surface of fibers. In the meanwhile, nanorods assembled to form spherical aggregation, looks like allium giganteum. So during the interface coating process, basically the nuclei of LaPO₄ crystal appears at the first two precipitations which arrayed compactly along the fibers. After several cycles, the new precipitate based on the initial nuclei, and then grow up to bigger spherical-shaped polycrystallines, which diameters are around 400~500 nm. In this procedure, slow rate of precipitation and plenary infiltration of solution is strongly required to form uniform coating.

Figure 2: Nuclei morphology of LaPO₄ on the alumina fiber at the 2nd and 4th precipitation

Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows the cross sections of alumina and quartz fabric preforms after 5 times precipitation respectively. The coating is uniform and the thickness is 200~400nm for alumina fabric preforms, rarely aggregation and enrichment is observed. While, the coating in quartz fabric preforms is a little bit thicker than in alumina fabric preform, and enrichment of LaPO₄ particles at the edge of fiber bundles performed obviously. Nevertheless, coatings for both kinds of preform are satisfied. These expected coating layers for the integrated fabric preform supply profitable interface for fiber reinforced composites, which will improve the mechanic properties of the composites.

Figure 3: Cross-section morphology of oLaPO₄ coating on alumina fabric preforms

Figure 4: Cross-section morphology of oLaPO₄ coating on quartz fabric preforms

3.2 Strength of alumina/quartz fiber with LaPO₄ coatings

The tensile strengths of alumina and quartz filament bundles are 1.7 GPa and 1.5 GPa. After LaPO₄ coatings, the tensile strengths at room temperature are 1.78 GPa and 1.43 GPa., nearly without any degradation. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show XRD patterns of coated and uncoated with LaPO₄ layers on alumina and quartz fibers results shows. LaPO₄ and γ -Al₂O₃ phase are detected in alumina fiber coated with LaPO₄. At the same time, LaPO₄ and amorphous silica phase are detected in quartz fiber coated with LaPO₄. Which means coating procedure retain the patterns of original fiber, and without any other phase produced. Therefore the strength and structure of fibers can be maintained.

Figure 5: XRD patterns of coated and uncoated with LaPO₄ layers on alumina fibers

Figure 6: XRD patterns of coated and uncoated with LaPO₄ layers on quartz fibers

3.3 High temperature stability of alumina/quartz fiber reinforced composites

Dense composites are obtained according the composites preparation procedure. The densities of the prepared alumina and quartz fiber reinforced composites are ~ 2.3 g/cm³ and 1.9 g/cm³. Figure 5 is the microstructure results of the deduced composite which shows the composite is uniform and dense.

Figure 7: Microstructure of alumina fiber (a) and quartz fiber (b) reinforced composites

The biggest advantage for LaPO_4 interface coating for alumina fiber and quartz fiber reinforced composites is the improvement of strength retention at high-temperature, especially at 1200°C . For alumina fiber reinforced composites, the room-temperature tensile strength of the composites without LaPO_4 interface is 120 MPa, modulus is 34 GPa, fracture strain is 0.5%. But at the 1200°C the tensile strength decrease a lot, which is 22.8 MPa, and modulus is 14 GPa, fracture strain is 0.11%. However, the mechanical properties at high temperature improve a lot when LaPO_4 interface coating is utilized. The tensile strength of alumina fiber reinforced composites with LaPO_4 interface is 38.6 MPa, modulus is 18.5 GPa, and fracture strain is 0.20%. Similar results present for quartz fiber reinforced composites. The tensile strength at 1200°C increase to 27.5 MPa compared to 17.3 MPa for the composites without LaPO_4 interface. In figure 8, tensile strength samples of alumina fiber reinforced composites are characterized by SEM. The fracture surface with LaPO_4 interface presents typical fibers pull-out behavior, whereas, the surface without LaPO_4 interface showed brittle morphology. Thereby, the interface plays a critical part in composites, toughening results essentially from sliding friction along the debonds within the coating.

Figure 8: Micro-morphology of fracture surface for alumina fiber reinforced composites with (a) and without (b) LaPO_4 interface coating

In addition, the XRD evolvments at 1200°C to 1400°C present the stability of alumina fiber reinforced composites. As figure 9 shows, 1200°C heat treatment for 1 hour will not change the diffraction pattern. When treatment temperature increase to 1300°C , mullite phase presents. This result implies that the composite shows good stability under 1200°C .

Figure 9: XRD patterns of alumina fiber reinforced composites under 1200, 1300 and 1400°C heat treatment for 1 hour

4 CONCLUSIONS

LaPO₄ interface coatings were applied to alumina and quartz fiber reinforced composites, which preparation procedure shows good infiltration performance for woven fabric preforms. The thickness of the LaPO₄ coating can be ranged from 200 nm~1.0 μm, and tensile strength of fiber without any degradation after the coating process. Moreover, the tensile strengths of both composites at high temperature are well optimized by utilizing the LaPO₄ coating. The results present that those composites have potential application in long service life at high temperature under the oxidation environment.

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